

EXAMINATION OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN READING ANXIETY AND SELF-EFFICACY PERCEPTION FOR READING COMPREHENSION IN 5th GRADE STUDENTS

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Abstract:

Reading is an important instrument that guides the individual on the way to learning. Comprehension, on the other hand, is a situation which is desired and expected to be attained as a result of reading. Therefore, the point where reading must reach is comprehension and correct interpretation of what is read. The aim of this study is to determine the level of reading anxiety and reading comprehension self-efficacy perception of 5th grade students and to set forth the relationships between these concepts if any. The sample group of the study consisted of 5th grade students studying in a secondary school randomly selected in the east in 2017-2018 school year. The data were collected using "Scale of Belief Self-Efficacy Reading Comprehension" developed by Epçaçan and Demirel (2011) and "Reading Anxiety Scale" developed by Çeliktürk and Yamaç (2015). According to the results obtained, reading anxiety levels of the students were found to be high. In addition, it was found that there were significant correlations between reading anxiety and self-efficacy perception for reading.

Keywords: reading, anxiety, self-efficacy perception, student

1. Introduction

Reading is an important language skill an individual needs throughout his/her life. Reading skill which is the easiest and most economical way of reaching information should be a skill starting in the family and being strengthened and improved by the individual during education life. *"Reading is an important skill which should be acquired both in school life and daily life. Raising individuals, who are capable of reading correctly and fluently, interpreting what they read and communicating them orally and in writing, is of great importance in terms of academic and social life of the person."* (Çeliktürk and Yamaç, 2015: 98). However, reading means not only reading certain texts but also the process of

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comprehending what is read and correct interpretation. *“Reading activity is an effective process that improves the knowledge capacity of the human, shapes his/her thoughts and beliefs, and impersonates him/her. This process is an intellectual activity where biological, psychological and physiological characteristics of the individual function in an effective integrity. What is inherent in this activity is the “goal of comprehending”* (Epeçan and Demirel, 2011: 120).

Reading is very important not only for obtaining information but also for personal development of an individual. Reading opens doors to new worlds furnishing the individual with different perspectives. It contributes to self-realisation of the individual. (Kurudayıoğlu and Çeliktürk, 2013). All previous experiences of the individual, either positive or negative, affect this skill as well just like in all cases. Of course, the individual should have physical, mental and psychological competences, just like in every skill. Because, an individual lacking such competences cannot be expected to make a healthy reading. However, if the person does not tend or cannot manage to read despite having those competences, there is a lack of motivation there which may turn into anxiety over time. This anxiety may adversely affect acquiring skills and improvement within the process. Negative experiences which cause anxiety affect the feelings and thoughts of the individual negatively and as a result, the individual considers himself/herself inadequate and incompetent in managing any negative situation (Bandura, 1997; Mills, Pajares and Herron, 2006).

Anxiety is negative feelings and thoughts developed by an individual towards a situation or an event. *“Anxiety is a mood leading individuals to sadness”* (Katrancı and Kuşdemir, 2015: 417). Anxiety arises as a response to a problem. Way of emergence of anxiety is deemed as worrying (such as cognitive responses, self-deprecating) or emotional (such as physical responses, faster heartbeats, blushing) (Leibert and Morris, 1967; Zeidner, 1998). It is agreed in the studies that anxiety is a negative feeling and it is also known that temporary anxiety level has a positive effect on learning or success of the individual whereas permanent anxiety has negative effects (Aşiloğlu and Özkan, 2013; Jalongo and Hirsh, 2010; Kahan, 2008; Donnelly, 2009).

Damage caused by constant anxiety to an individual, after a while causes perception of the situation which caused anxiety to be completely negative and turns it into a behaviour. *“Behaviours of an anxious person deteriorate and what have been learnt by the person lose effectiveness.”* (Tekindal, 2009:9).

Reading anxiety, on the other hand, forms the basis for all kinds of problems regarding reading as a result of negative experiences of the individual on this skill. According to Murray and Janelle (2003), reading anxiety that has gained continuity causes falling away from reading and failure in time. Because Mohammadpur and Ghafournia (2015) reported this situation by stating that there is a negative relationship between reading levels and reading anxiety of students. This, over time, weakens self-belief and self-potential of the individual and damages self-efficacy for reading.

Self-efficacy, on the other hand, refers to *“judgements of the people on their skills for organising and exhibiting actions that will enable them to reach a certain performance”* (Saracaloğlu, Karasakaloğlu and Gencel, 2010:266). That is to say, self-efficacy can be described as a person’s knowing what to do and to what extent to do it and use this

knowledge in acquiring experience. Zimmerman (1995) describes self-efficacy perception as to what extent the individuals are competent about their skills which may affect the result of an action, behaviour or situation, but not the said skills themselves. In other words, the answer by the individuals to the question “*what can I do about this work or to what extent can I do*” will certainly include the level of self-efficacy. Because, while positive motivation results in self-efficacy success, negative self-efficacy would result in failure (Bandura, 1997).

In the light of the aforementioned, it was tried to find out the relationship between reading anxiety and reading comprehension self-efficacy perception of the 5th grade students who are deemed as secondary school 1st grade. The reason for preferring 5th grade is that the 5th graders are students who have completed primary education, have an infrastructure for skill acquisition, and are now in the process of developing this. The study is different from other studies since reading anxiety and reading comprehension are studied together. In this regard, it is expected to contribute to literature.

2. Method

In this study, it was aimed to investigate the relationship between reading anxiety and reading self-efficacy perception of 5th grade students. Since it was tried in the study to describe the existing situation as it was, the study was structured in survey model. Survey model refers to the studies “*which are usually conducted with relatively larger samples compared to other studies and where opinions or interests, skills, abilities, attitudes and similar characteristics of the participants regarding any subject or event are determined*” (Büyüköztürk, Kılıç Çakmak, Akgün, Karadeniz and Demirel; 2014: 177). It is tried to express the individual or the object, which is the subject of the study, within his/its own conditions and as he/it is (Karasar, 2010).

“*Correlational survey approach, which is the survey approach aiming to determine existence of covariance between two or more variables, was used in the study*” (Karasar, 2005: 81). Correlational analysis can be made in two ways as correlation and comparison type relationship (Karasar, 2005). In this research, correlational survey took place as the correlational survey model. Correlational research is the studies conducted to determine the correlations between two or more variables and to obtain the cause and effect clues (Büyüköztürk, Çakmak, Akgün, Karadeniz and Demirel, 2011:14).

2.1 The Sample Group

The sample group consisted of 5th grade students who were studying in a secondary school in a city centre in the east in 2017-2018 school year and selected randomly. Table 1 shows information on demographic characteristics of the students.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of the teachers in the sample group

Demographic Characteristics		Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Female	74	61.7
	Male	46	38.3
	Total	120	100.0

2.2 Data Collection Tools

A. Reading Anxiety Scale: The scale developed by Çeliktürk and Yamaç (2015) consists of 29 items and a single subscale. The scale having a 5-point likert structure is scored from 5 (Always) – 1 (Never). Cronbach’s Alpha internal consistency reliability coefficient of the scale was indicated as .95. According to DFA results, following values were determined for the study; RMSEA .76, CFI .97, and NFI .95. The current form of the scale was accepted to be valid and reliable.

B. The Scale of Belief Self-Efficacy Reading Comprehension: The scale developed by Epçaçan and Demirel (2011) consists of 27 articles and 3 subscales. 5-point likert type scale is scored as 1 “I am absolutely not sure”, 2 “I am barely sure”, 3 “I am slightly sure”, 4 “I am quite sure”, 5 “I am completely sure”. The subscales of the scale are named as “Written and Visual Comprehension”, “Self-Regulation in Reading”, and “High Self-Confidence for Reading”. Cronbach’s Alpha internal consistency reliability coefficient of the scale was determined to be .88. The current form of the scale was accepted to be valid and reliable.

3. Results

Mean values were examined in order to determine the levels of reading anxiety and reading self-efficacy perception of the 5th grade students. Table 2 shows the results.

Table 2: Mean values

Variables	N	$\bar{X}$	Sd
WVC	120	41.97	4.58
SRR	120	35.22	3.90
HSCFR	120	28.66	4.18
RAS	120	112.05	11.62

While maximum score to be received from WVC “written and visual comprehension” subscale of the scale of belief self-efficacy reading comprehension is 55, minimum score is 11. When examining the table, mean scores of the students for this subscale were observed to be high. While the highest score to be received from SRR “self-regulation in reading” subscale of the same scale is 45, the lowest score is 9. It was observed that the students had high mean score in this subscale. While the highest score to be received from “high self-confidence for reading” HSCFR, the final subscale of the same scale, is 35, the lowest score is 7. Also, the students had high mean scores in this subscale. In addition, the highest score to be obtained from the reading anxiety scale (RAS) is 145 and the lowest score is 29. When examining the table, it was observed that mean scores

of the students were high and this can be asserted to be a negative result for students since anxiety is in question. *“As the anxiety mean score increases, level of anxiety increases as well”* (Maden and Durukan, 2016:1952).

In order to analyse the relationship between reading anxiety and reading self-efficacy perception of the 5th grade students, Pearson’s correlation coefficients were calculated in the study. Table 3 shows the results.

Table 3: Correlations

Variables	2	3	4
1. WVC	.695**	.598**	.872**
2. SRR		.750**	.912**
3. HSCFR			.860**
4. RAS			

**p<.01, *p<.05

When examining the correlation coefficients, it was found that there was a quite high positive correlation and positive high correlation between reading anxiety and reading self-efficacy perception and positive high and moderate correlations were observed between subscales of the scale of belief self-efficacy reading comprehension.

According to Table 3, it was found that there was a quite high positive significant correlation ($r=.912^{**}$) between reading anxiety and “self-regulation in reading” SRR, one of the subscales of the scale of belief self-efficacy reading comprehension. There was a high positive significant correlation between reading anxiety and “written and visual comprehension” WVC ($r=.872^{**}$) subscale of the scale of belief self-efficacy reading comprehension and between reading anxiety and “high self-confidence for reading” HSCFR ($r=.860^{**}$) subscale of the scale of belief self-efficacy reading comprehension. On the other hand, it was found that there were a high positive significant correlation between “self-regulation in reading-SRR” subscale and “high self-confidence for reading HSCFR ($r=.750^{**}$) subscale among the subscales of the scale of belief self-efficacy reading comprehension and also a high positive significant correlation between the subscales “self-regulation in reading-SRR” and “written and visual comprehension-WVC” ($r=.695^{**}$). Finally, a moderate positive correlation was determined between “high self-confidence for reading-HSCFR” and “written and visual comprehension-WVC, the subscales of the scale of belief self-efficacy reading comprehension.

In order to find out whether or not the variables predicted each other, multiple linear regression analysis was made. Table 4 shows the results.

Table 4: Results of multiple linear regression analysis

Variables	β	F	R	R ²	p
WVC	.412*				
SRR	.378*				
HSCFR	.331*	250.83	.994	.988	.000
Gender	.004				

*p<.05

When examining the data obtained as a result of multiple linear regression analysis in Table 4, p value of .000 showed that the regression model was significant. It was observed in the table that reading anxiety of the 5th grade students were significantly predicted by their self-efficacy perception for reading. When examining R² value, it was understood that 98% of listening self-efficacy (R²=.98) was predicted by subscales of the scale of belief self-efficacy reading comprehension. In analysis of standardised regression coefficients, it was determined that “written and visual comprehension-WVC” ($\beta = .412^*$) subscale of the scale of belief self-efficacy reading comprehension ranked first as the predictor of reading anxiety. “Self-regulation in reading-SRR” ($\beta = .378^*$) and “high self-confidence for reading-HSCFR” subscales of the same scale, were also predictors of reading anxiety. According to the table, it was determined that gender was not a significant predictor of reading anxiety ($\beta = .004$).

4. Conclusion and Discussion

In the study, it was aimed to determine reading anxiety and reading self-efficacy perception in 5th grade students. Accordingly, first mean scores received by the students from reading anxiety scale and the scale of belief self-efficacy reading comprehension was examined. In the light of the obtained results, it was found that reading anxiety mean scores of the students were high. Since anxiety came into question, this was a negative conclusion for the students. Because increasing anxiety mean score also revealed that the students acquired negative experiences for reading. High anxiety level adversely affects learning in general, and improvement of reading skill in particular (Murray and Janelle, 2003, Cited by Melanlıoğlu, 2014). On the other hand, reading self-efficacy perception of the students was found to be high for all subscales. This was a positive result for students. Reading is a concept which should be acquired and handled meticulously as it is both among the language skills and one of the conditions and instruments for an individual to be successful. Various studies reveal that high anxiety level affects learning process negatively and causes decrease in desired efficiency (Williams, Vickers and Rodrigues, 2002; Murray and Janelle, 2003; Eysenck and Payne, 2006). On the other hand, academic success of individuals who have acquired reading skill properly and have improved this skill, is also high. However, more important matter is that reading is an everlasting need. In other words, the case should be examined not only with regard to academic success but also in terms of continuous development. Because, if such negative situations of students with reading anxiety are not changed in early periods, conclusions which may affect negatively their entire lives may occur (Grills-Taquechel, Fletcher, Vaughn and Stuebing, 2012; Torgesen, Wagner and Rashotte, 1994). As a result of the study by Kuşdemir and Katranç (2016) it was found that reading comprehension scores of 4th grade students of the primary school were moderate; whereas, reading anxiety scores were low.

Another subject examined in the study was whether or not there was any correlation between reading anxiety and reading self-efficacy perception. As a result of the analysis, very high positive and high correlations were found between reading

anxiety scale and the scale of belief self-efficacy reading comprehension. Based on these correlations, it is possible to state that as the related potential of the students regarding reading who have self-regulation skill in reading, in other words, who know their potential for reading and shape learning process accordingly increases, their reading anxiety level increases as well. It is possible to state that as regards the students who have written and visual comprehension skills, in other words, who can turn the texts they read into new knowledge and concepts by strengthening them with former knowledge they have and have visual reading skill; as these skills of these students increase, their reading anxiety also increases. Finally, it is possible to assert that self-beliefs of the students who have high self-confidence in reading and are self-confident in this regard increase, their reading anxiety also increases. This result is remarkable. Low anxiety levels for students, particularly who know themselves in terms of reading and have potential, is an expected result. Higher reading anxiety level is not a desired result. Because, as reading anxiety level increases, the level of acquiring this skill and then becoming successful decreases. Anxiety will cause negative processes and acquisitions regarding the skill. Kuşdemir and Katrancı (2016) found in their study that there was a negative weak significant correlation between reading anxiety and reading comprehension skill. As a result of the study by Baki (2017) it was concluded that reading anxiety and attitude towards reading affect reading habit directly and significantly. In the study by Arslan (2017) it was found that there was a negative moderate correlation between reading anxiety and academic self-efficacy of students.

Finally, it was examined in the study whether or not reading anxiety of students was predicted by the variables of reading self-efficacy perception and gender. According to the results, reading anxiety was found to be predicted by reading self-efficacy perception but not by the variable of gender. According to this result, it is possible to state that as the skills and potential of students for reading increase, their reading anxiety increases as well. Kurudayıoğlu and Çelik (2013) found in their study that reading education perception of students did not show any significant difference in terms of the variable of gender. Topçuoğlu Ünal and Sever (2013) concluded in their study that reading self-efficacy of students did not show any significant difference in terms of the variable of gender.

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